
MODERNIST AESTHETICS IN MODERN AFRICAN POETRY

IMO EKPE OKON (Ph.D)

Department of English, University of Uyo, Nigeria
Email: ekpeimo@gmail.com Phone: +2348134970796

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PRINCE OGHENETEGHA OHWAVWORHUA

Department of English and Literary Studies
Delta State University Abraka
Email: princeohwos@gmail.com Phone: +2349066793471

Abstract

This paper examines modernist aesthetics in modern African poetry. The aim of this undertaking is predicated on the background that modern African poetry is a continuum of the 20th century European modernist literature. A study of this nature is significant because it critically hints on the origin of modern African poetry, its canonisation, and its future as a literary form. The study starts with an examination of the concepts of ‘modern’ and ‘modernism’, first as separate terminologies and then as interwoven concepts. The paper further examines the nature and form of modern African poetry and poses the questions of “what makes African poetry ‘modern’?” and “is African poetry a continuum of European modernist poetry?” In answering these questions, this paper examines some forms of modernism in modern African poetry such as syntactic inversion and jugglery, fragmentation, vivid imagery/imagism, symbolism, and allusiveness. Selected poems by Soyinka, Okara, Clark, Okigbo and Echeruo have been used for analysis. The study has shown that, truly, modernism exists as a concept in modern African poetry and its features have greatly influenced the modern shape of African poems.

Keywords: Modernism, Modern African Poetry, Wole Soyinka, Christopher Okigbo, J. P. Clark

1 Introduction

This paper examines modernist aesthetics in modern African poetry, its manifestations, and its role in the contemporary shape of African poetry. The significance of this paper is predicated upon the need to understand the factors,

both internal and external, that gave rise to the literary manifestation known as modern African poetry. This paper is aimed at underscoring those salient “modernist” features, themes, and techniques that dominate African poetry. African written poetic tradition usually takes the modifier “modern”. This term is loaded and suggests a whole lot of things. Questions arise when the critical reader stumbles upon the terms “Modern African Poetry” and “Modernist African Poetry”. These questions include; are the concepts of ‘modern African poetry’ and ‘modernist African poetry’ the same? What is ‘modern’ about African poetry? Is modern African poetry the same as modernism in African poetry? What are the peculiarities of modernism in African poetry? Are all African poems modern? Is modernism a style, technique, phase or a movement in African poetry? However, before proceeding into historical and poetic analyses in a bid to answer salient questions, it is appropriate that the operational terms be clarified, especially with regards to the scope of this paper.

2 The Concepts of Modern And Modernism

The terms modern and modernism are quite related and intertwined yet they mean different things if their meanings are extended. Fiyinfoluwa believes that the term ‘modern’ is “synonymous to new or recent” (2). This view is quite simplistic however; it captures the nature of that term. Hooti and Omrani (252) assert that the term ‘modern’ generally refers to ‘anything done or produced at the contemporary period’. Many dictionaries and encyclopaedias simply use the term to refer to something new, as against an older tradition. In this sense, anything modern is new, fresh, and juxtaposed against the old. This view of the term ‘modern’ can be described as the layman’s perspective. In the context of Africa, Nwoga asserts that the term ‘modern’ refers to a work which is written (33). This view is predicated against the traditional oral modes in African societies. However, this term came into common parlance as a result of something. The phenomenon that birthed the word “modern” can be traced to the early 20th century when the literary movement known as ‘modernism’ was birthed because of various socio-political circumstances. These circumstances influenced the philosophy, literature, culture, music, visual arts, and virtually all aspects of human society. Dobrinescu asserts that the term ‘modernism’ is derived from the term ‘modern’ (316).

Kiran believes that the term ‘modernism’ is used “to distinguish the literature that developed out of the First World War” and that it “challenged all the old modes [of thinking]” (176). This view is predicated on periodisation. Many critics emphasise that the period of Modernism was at its peak in the Pre-War years while others believe that it was at the peak in the Post-War years (Brooker 4). However, for the purpose of this paper, this period is presumed to have started in the second decade of the 20th century. Bradbury and McFarlane assert that the period of modernism breaks away from traditional views and examines man’s conditions and functions in life (26). This period brought about an unprecedented spurt of development in the fields of technology, psychology, computing, physics, chemistry, biology, art, music and virtually every aspect of available knowledge. Some of the major developments in this period include; Freudian psychoanalysis, the development of Penicillin, Einstein’s theory of relativity, the invention of the aeroplane and the modern car, the development of the first computers, the invention of nuclear energy and nuclear weaponry, the development of Quantum theory, and the upsurge of *avant-garde* techniques in visual arts, music and literature, among others. Apart from these, the World Wars also etched an indelible mark on the psyche on the 20th century men. For the first time, the totality of man’s wickedness and inclination to destructiveness was unearthed and man began to question the role of God in the turmoil of the world. These developments overwhelmed mankind and man started to question his place in the universe, the existence of God, the purpose of life and the interconnectedness of everything that exists. These questions gave rise to various philosophical and artistic spin-offs of modernism. These “spin-offs” include; Existentialism, Absurdism, Imagism, Dadaism, Surrealism, Cubism, Futurism, Minimalism, Expressionism, among others. These “isms” used *avant-garde* methods to question, answer and examine the human condition.

In literature, modernism left its indelible touch. It is known that literature does not exist in a vacuum and that all works are products of tensions, trends and developments in the socio-political terrain. This view has already been asserted in equivocal terms by NgugiwaThiong’o (xv) when he says “literature does not exist in a vacuum”. Modernist literature developed as a direct result of the socio-political considerations captured above. Modernism in Literature manifested in the form of new literary techniques and forms and a rebellion against standard conventions and realism. Each literary genre had its own

unique developments. However, in poetry which we are concerned with, developments in versification, thematic thrusts, form and techniques were noticeable. Some of the features of modernist poetry have been captured by Bachelor and master thus:

In poetry, we can discuss the modernist elements in terms of four major subheadings: modern or new experiments in form and style, new themes and word-games, new modes of expression, and complex and open-ended nature of their themes and meaning. The most striking element of modernist poetry is the invention and experimentation of new modes of expression. [...] The different ways of expressing include the imagist way of presenting just concrete images for the readers to understand the idea and experience the feelings themselves; the symbolist way of presenting things in terms of deeply significant symbols of ideas and feelings for readers to interpret them intellectually; the realist way of truly reflecting the reality of the world; the naturalist way of going to the extreme of realism by showing the private, psychological, fantastic and the neurotic; the impressionistic way of presenting unrefined first impression of everything by the observer; the expressionistic way of probing deep into one's own psyche and trying to express the hidden and deepest feelings, as in confessional poems; the surrealist way of imposing the mood of madness, intoxication and neurosis to excite the illogical 'language' of the unconscious; to name a few (pars. 1-3).

It is obvious that the citation above surmises the main standpoints of modernist poetry. Abrams also adds to this by asserting that in modernist poetry, "standard syntactic flow of poetic language" was replaced by "fragmented utterances" and "coherent poetic structure" replaced by "deliberate dislocation of facts" (167). Modernist poets used private and esoteric personae, copious allusions and symbolisms, vivid imagery and sound, open-ended thematic thrusts and experimentations with form to convey the individualistic conflicts exacerbated by the turmoil of the world. Some of the modernist poets include; T.S. Eliot, Ezra Pound, W.B. Yeats, W.H. Auden, G.M. Hopkins and E.E. Cummings, among others.

Modernism, however, was a global phenomenon. It was not experienced by only a single nation. Its literary manifestation found home in all national literature(s). However, in Africa, the historical Modernism was a bit too early yet its influence cannot be negated. This is what informs the crux of this paper.

3 **Modernist Aesthetics and Modern African Poetry**

“Modern African Poetry” is a product of three distinct terms. These terms must be isolated before their meaning in connected context can be put together. Firstly, the term ‘modern’ has been examined before. However, for the purpose of this context, the term is used to mean “written” and “contemporary” as averred by Nwoga (33) and Hooti and Omrani (252). The term ‘African’ is used in this context to refer to anything emanating from the African continent, by an African and for Africans. Poetry, as is known, is a genre of literature in which words are rhythmically arranged into verses, injected with emotions and distinct language, in other to entertain, teach and instruct. If these terms are put together, modern African poetry simply means written poetry emanating from Africa, written by Africans, for Africans and handling the African experience. This view, however, may be seen as simplistic. It is therefore apt to present some scholarly definitions of modern African poetry.

Finyinfolowa asserts that modern African poetry can be seen as a discipline of study and as the art of versifying. According to him:

Modern African Poetry can be seen from two dimensions, which are: Modern African Poetry as a field of study (discipline) and Modern African Poetry as the art of versifying. The former captures the totality of the African creative quintessence in verse form. It encapsulates the creative process of writing poems on the African continent; from Accra to Soweto and Mogadishu to Cairo devoid of technical definitions regarding what makes an African poem African. On the other hand, modern African Poetry as a discipline defines what makes a poem and a poet African by setting parameters for its evaluation and exploring themes fundamental to its emergence and existence (1).

In the same vein, Okunoye avers that modern African poetry is “defined in relation to European literary traditions which provide the paradigms,

conventions and critical principles that are either appropriated or negated in the process of defining the identity of the newer literatures” (770). This view situates African poetry within the framework of European literature. Consequently, African poetry becomes a continuum of the European modernist tradition. If this is so, certain questions arise. Some of these questions have been asked by James Tsaaior and they include; “who and what determine what is the modern period in African poetry [...]?” and “can ‘modern’ and ‘contemporary’ be used synonymously? Whether or not modern African poetry is canonised in European modernist literature, it does not negate the fact that it is unique, distinct and has evolved separately and in unique socio-political climates.

Okon attempts a taxonomy of modern African poetry by dividing it into phases. These phases/periods are labelled thus; “the pioneers”, “the nationalists”, “the older generation”, and the “younger generation” (95-109). Okon’s taxonomy is not isolated. Other writers have canonised African poetic works into various phases in their own ways. Nwoga did this in his anthology, *West African Verse*, where he classifies modern African poetry into the “pioneer” phase and the “modern” phase (121-142). Bamgbose (2-10) and Olowookere (162-169) are also among scholars who have attempted canonising modern African poetry.

Drawing from the preceding, it is important to underscore, at this point, that the pioneer modern African poets wrote rudimentary poems with political undertones and ideologies. They were more or less concerned with nationalism and the agitation for political independence. Others were concerned with Africa and her image. Some of these poets include; Michael Dei-Anang, Gladys CaselyHayford, Dennis Osadebay, R.E.G. Armattoo, Leopold Sedar Senghor, and others. Their poems are accessible, simplistic, romantic, and ideological. However, from the 1950s, a new crop of poets started to express themselves. These poets have been referred to as the “older generation” (Okon 101). Other critics like Olaoluwa (2) use the term “first generation” poets. However, it is commonly agreed that this generation of poets used “Eurocentric” styles to write. Chinweizu, Jemie and Madubuike (183) put this in better light by asserting that the poets wrote using “an alien technique, based on an alien sensitivity that is rather too formalist, ambiguity for ambiguity’s sake, sprung rhythm for sprung rhythm’s sake, etc obscure them as they try to present or explore thoughts that are rooted in the traditional African setting”.

They go further to assert that the poet wrote using “ambiguities, syntactical jugglery with suppression of auxiliary verb and articles, the spacious and contorted cadences of sprung rhythm, the heavy use of alliteration and assonance within a line...” (183). These poets have been accused of obscurantism by Aiyejina (112) and other critics. Their poetry is private, esoteric, allusive, inaccessible, avant-garde, cumbersome, and experimental. Okonavers, “the older generation was composed of early poet whose visions were private and individualistic. They showed, at best, only social concern but never preached revolution or adopted any form of ideology” (101). The poets have been accused of copying the practices of 20th century European poetry and poets like Hopkins, Pounds, and Eliot by Chinweizu, Jemie and Madubuike (163). Some of these poets include Gabriel Okara, J.P. Clark, Wole Soyinka, EzenwaOhaeto, Christopher Okigbo, M.J.C. Echeruo, Mac Akpoyovwaire, and a host of others. Most of these poets wrote in literary journals published in Ibadan. The journals are *Black Orpheus* (Edited by UlliBeier) and *The Horn* (Edited by Martin Banham).

It is obvious that European Modernism has influenced modern African poetry, especially the poetry of the first generation of poets. However, the specific forms in which these influences manifest are addressed in this paper. The poems are drawn largely from Okigbo, Soyinka and Clark. The elements that are examined include; syntactic inversion and jugglery (Hopkinsian syntax), allusiveness, fragmentation, vivid imagery and symbolism.

Syntactic Inversion and Jugglery

Syntactic inversion is an element of modernism employed by modernist poets like G.M. Hopkins. It usually involves the inversion of the subject and the predicate in a verse. Syntactic jugglery involves moving the lexical and functional elements of a clause anywhere, without restraints, in a verse. This modernist technique is frequently used by Christopher Okigbo and Wole Soyinka. Okigbo’s “The Passage” is a good example of this. Okigbo uses this modernist style to heighten the obscurantist effect of his poem. The very first few lines are syntactically inverted through the technique of anastrophe thus: “Before you, mother Idoto, / naked I stand, / before your watery presence, / a prodigal...” (Soyinka 295). The lines above have been inverted by the poet as a means of creating a sense of esotericism, of things beyond the nature. The lines should have been “I stand naked/ before you/ mother Idoto...” but the poet

has juggled and inverted this syntax as much as Hopkins does. This is the main reason why Okigbo is said to be suffering from “Hopkins disease” by Chinweizu, Jemie and Madubuike.

Syntactic inversion is generally used by modernist poets to convey the sense of chaos and disorder in the world. They use their poems to metaphorically represent the traditional order and the juggled syntax represents the decline to confusion and the rebellion against that order. This syntactic jugglery is found all through the poem “The Passage”. However, another notable instance is in lines 7-8 where the poet persona says “Under your power wait I/ on barefoot...” (295). This line should have been rendered traditionally thus: “I wait under your power/ on barefoot...” This deviation has established itself as a protest to the norms of the world. This is a salient point in modernist poetry and Okigbo has used his poems, especially “The Passage”, to exemplify the influence of modernism in his poetry.

Allusiveness

Abrams (9) defines allusion as “a passing reference, without explicit identification, to a literary or historical person, place, or event, or to another literary work or passage.” Allusiveness, therefore, is a copious reliance on allusions in a work. This may be done by the poet in order to intertextualise the poems with classical or extant works of art, persons or places. In modernist poetry, allusiveness is usually accredited to T.S. Eliot whose poems usually convey Biblical allusions, symbols, and undertones. Ezra Pound is also extremely allusiveness, especially to classical works. John Pepper Clark, Christopher Okigbo and Wole Soyinka are known for their copious use of allusions in their poetry. J.P. Clark’s poem “Olokun” makes use of some Biblical allusions. In the poem, the poet persona intertextualises his worship of the goddess ‘Olokun’ with that of the Christian God. This is seen in lines 6-7 of the poem; “I am jealous and passionate/ Like Jehovah, God of the Jews...” (Senanu and Vincent 207). This allusion to Christianity is not an isolated act. Clark is only continuing with the tradition of T.S. Eliot who is known to make copious biblical allusions which are predominant in his poem, “Journey of the Magi”. Clark uses these allusions to question religion and its roles in the modern world. Modernist poets, it has been said, questioned God and religion and attempted to revolt against religious doctrines. Clark has done this by his use of simile in linking Olokun and God. Other allusions in the poem

include “But what wakeful eyes of man, / Made of the mud of this earth...” (Lines 11-12), which alludes to the Biblical creation story where Man is said to have been created by the dust of the earth, and “So drunken, like ancient walls/ We crumble in heaps at your feet” (Lines 16-17) which alludes to the crumbling of the walls of Jericho in the Bible.

Fragmentation

Fragmentation simply means to cut short. Ideas or sentences are not completed but are simply left hanging or stopped abruptly. Fragmentation can occur at the structural level of the poem, i.e. a fragmented poem like T.S. Eliot’s “The Waste Land”, or at the level of the verse or stanzas. Fragmentation is used as a poetic device by modernists to assert the shortness of life and existence. This is against the background of strife, war and death that plagued the world at the heyday of the modernist period. Poets used this technique to assert the inevitability of death and loss. In modern African poetry, Wole Soyinka and Christopher Okigbo use this technique copiously. Soyinka uses fragmentation to obscure his intentions and cause the reader to reflect on what has not been said. This is in line with the modernist tradition. In his poem “To my First White Hairs”, Soyinka uses fragmentation to heighten effect and establish musing. The first stanza is used to defend this thus;

*Hirsute hell chimney-spouts, black thunderthroes confluence
of coarse cloudfleeces – my head sir! - scourbrush in bitumen,
past fossil beyond fingers of light –until ...!
(Senanu and Vincent 192)*

The extracted stanza above has structural fragmentation, stanzaic fragmentation and line fragmentation. Structurally, the poem does not cohere. Each line expresses different fragment of ideas, each stanza does the same. Thus, the whole poem is a cesspool of various fragments that must be reflected upon before any meaning can be realised. At the level of the stanza, the idea that a stanza is meant to present is lacking. The stanza is virtually meaningless as a result of the fragmentation. In fact, the poet ends the stanza with the elliptical indicator [...] to show that the stanza is a fragment. There is also no connection that makes a single line express a single idea. The first line, for instance, is “Hirsute hell chimney-spouts, black thunderthroes” (192). This line is fragmentary and the comma (,) serves to show that the line is divided into two fragmented parts like the caesura of old English poetry. This use of

fragmentation places the poem in the Eurocentric obscurantist tradition as opposed to the simplistic and communal African traditional poems.

Vivid Imagery

Imagery is an aspect of poetry that makes use of the senses to heighten the whole effect of a poem. A poet can use the senses of sight, touch, smell, taste, and hearing to good use in a poem. Modernist poets utilised this to a fault. Modernism birthed a movement known as Imagism in which a visual scene is rendered “as precisely and tersely as possible, and without comment or generalization [...] by means of metaphor, or by juxtaposing, without indicating a relation, the description of one object with that of a second and diverse object” (Abrams 122). Modern African poets did not employ Imagism to a fault like Ezra Pounds. However, their use of imagery, especially visual, is foregrounded, unique, and vivid. Modernist poets subscribe to the opinion that poetry is best communicated by sound and picture. The picture element of Modernist poetry is realised through vivid imagery. These imageries are so vivid because the poet persona devotes time to paint a perfect picture using each word, phrase, clause, line, and stanza. Nothing is used that is not visual in nature. This visual imagery resulted, historically, from the invention of cinematography and motion pictures. Modernist poets started to paint mental motion pictures for their reader.

One of the poets who employ vivid imagery is Michael Echeruo. In his poems, visual imagery is used to mental project the reader into his psychic atmosphere. He does this exceedingly well in his poem, “Outsider”, where the poet persona uses the vivid visual imagery to transport the reader’s mind. The very first stanza of the poem goes thus: “Between the oyster-beach and the greens... / Sea and barren coast. / Between tresses of dark silver and reels of danger... / lonesome bird of the wilds!” (Nwoga 82). The poet has used vivid visual imagery here to paint a picture of nature, of a natural ambient environment. This device situates the poet within the tradition of Ezra Pounds. Even beyond the use of visual imagery, Echeruo also employs auditory imagery in the secondary stanza (lines 6-7) thus: “Shouted at the moon from between my lungs, / Hooted at the chirrupy mermaid of the dusk...” (82). One cannot help but notice the perfect blend of audio-visual imagery in these lines. The poet immerses the reader into the world of magic, wonder, and excitement. This is the true strength of the Modernist poet!

Symbolism

A symbol is defined by Abrams as “a word or phrase that signifies an object or event which in its turn signifies something, or has a range of reference, beyond itself” (311). Symbolism is simply the process in which a writer uses words, phrases, verses or images to represent something beyond what is seen. Modernist poets popularised the use of symbolism in European literature. Essentially, poets of the modern period wrote to conceal their thoughts, rather than express it. This private and individualistic style of writing presents a problem to the reader. The reader has to unveil meaning through the identification of peculiar words, phrases, refrains, images, sounds, verses, etc. After identifying them, the reader has to interpret them in line with what they represent in the work. This is one of the reasons why critics say modernist poets are obscurantist, esoteric, private, and symbolic. In modern African poetry, symbolism has been used by the first generation poets to conceal their thoughts. Certain items attain significance based on the context and nature of their usage and they become symbols. These symbols represent something. It may be personal, collective, arbitrary, conventional, natural, mystical, spiritual, etc. Some poets who deploy symbolism copiously include Gabriel Okara, Christopher Okigbo and Wole Soyinka.

Okara’s “Piano and Drums” is full of symbols. Okara has deployed symbols in this poem in order to conceal his thoughts on one hand and unearth the vast expanse of collective interpretation it can be given on the other hand. In this poem, words, images, and sounds have been used as symbols. In the first stanza, the poet persona says “I hear jungle drums telegraphing / the mystic rhythm, urgent, raw / like bleeding flesh, speaking of / primal youth and the beginning,” (Nwoga 36). This “jungle drum” is used to symbolise the continent of Africa, together with her qualities of youthfulness, vitality and strength. The poet persona uses the audio-visual imagery to enhance this symbolism so much that any African can identify with the poem. The poet persona introduces another symbol in the third stanza of the poem “Then I hear a wailing piano / solo speaking of complex ways / in a tear-furrowed concerto;” (36). The use of “piano” here symbolises European ideals and values. The poet has used auditory imagery perfectly to enhance this symbolism. The poet persona, although writes about “drums” and “piano”, has used the modernist technique of symbolism to warp his poem and conceal his intentions through deliberate use of symbols. This is akin to what one sees in the poetry of William Butler

Yeats.

4 Conclusion

The foregoing has attempted to examine the concepts of “modern” and “modernism” as distinct terms and as interwoven concepts. Modernism as a historical, cultural, and literary movement has been addressed briefly as well. This paper has also examined the nature and form of modern African poetry as well as its first generation of poets. It has been found out that modern African poetry, in some ways, is a continuum of the 20th century European modernist poetry and that the poets of the first generation have copiously adapted from, imitated, and implemented the styles of the European modernist poets. This has earned them the name as “Eurocentric” poets. Some of the denominators of modernism in modern African poetry have been assessed and they include; syntactic jugglery, vivid imagery, symbolism, allusiveness and fragmentation. Selected poems have been used for analysis in order to defend the stand that modernism has truly influenced modern African poetry.

A critical reader would have noticed that this paper used poems mainly from Nigeria for analysis. This is not an anomaly; neither was it done in error. The written tradition of poetry in Anglophone Africa evolved, as we know it, in Nigeria around the 1950s. The poets who wrote at this time read the works of European modernist poets and attempted to write like them. These poets are the ones who have been treated in this study. By the time other countries began to catch up, peculiar African aesthetics had evolved and these modernist styles were relegated in favour of themes. It should also be noted that other contemporary poems may possess elements of modernism. However, as far as modernism is concerned in African poetry, we are concerned largely with the first generation of poets. It is hoped that this paper has been able to answer the questions; what is modern in modern African poetry? and is African poetry a continuum of the European tradition of modernism? This researcher advocates for further research on the elements of European modernism and postmodernism in contemporary African poetry. This is because no matter how “African” our poetry has become, we have been and shall always be constrained to the European forms with which we have started with and consequently, our poems shall adapt and adopt some of the styles found in European contemporary poetry.

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